

Contratonality and multitonality as new solutions to the crisis of tonality in art music

Marin Bilić

ABSTRACT

The development of art music throughout the 20th century was marked by a gradual decadence and rejections of tonal values, sometimes even the tone itself. This approach to music was essentially shaped by the cultural and political struggles that marked the 20th century, after which the view that the possibilities of tonality are exhausted has dominated to this day. This article deals with the unexplored parts of tonality and for the first time will propose a direct definition of the origin of tonality. The new tonal system proposed in this article is called contratonality, and its existence is based on the opposite values from which tonality developed, thus complementing the theory of classical harmony. This system of dissonance, as opposed to tonality, the system of consonance, was indirectly initiated in the 20th century by the work of Béla Bartók, although Bartók did not shape it into a harmonic system itself. With this theory comes the possibility of existence of multiple tonal systems, which will be discussed.

KEYWORDS

Contratonality, multitonality, Gesamtmusikwerk, quadrivium, kitsch, acoustic scale, consonance and dissonance, avant-garde music, musical heptagram

Introduction

This work is based on the confrontation of Western music with its deep crisis of tonality and culture, together with the awareness of the unexplored parts of tonality. This theme is very rare because since Theodor Adorno it has been considered that the possibilities of tonality are exhausted, which is why, in his opinion, tonal music can only go into banality and cliché.¹

The aforementioned form of cultural state is very rare in the history of music, and its dominance began after World War II. The reaction to the collectively experienced terror and trauma is formed through the negation and rejection of the cultural identity of the West and the beginning of an aesthetic revolution, primarily through avant-garde music. The entire movement will experience its culmination after World War II in Germany, where influences and ideas will be defined through the Darmstadt School. However, the newly emerging culture will remain dominant until today, maintaining the same value foundations as an uninterrupted attack on fundamental Western values, which will later be shaped from avant-garde music into the definition of postmodernism. Art music, both directly and indirectly, becomes based on ideological tendencies and systematic demolition, rejection of every system of formation in music and art, thus losing its objectivity and independence.

The work also contains a proposal for new musical concepts and will, for the first time, propose a direct definition of the origin of tonality, as well as other possibilities, paths, and new systems that music can take.

¹ ADORNO (1958, 2007), 22.

1 Culturicide as a prelude to World War II

The political ideas and movements of the late 18th and 19th centuries undoubtedly influenced the structure of modern civilization, including music.² They often served as inspiration for many composers of that period, from Beethoven to Wagner. However, they remained only at the level of inspiration. Composers pushed form and other musical elements to their limits, but did not reject any element, however drastic and significant the changes were in some compositions.

With the advent of the industrial revolution, the previous definition that art is a virtue found within man, which is only recognized and manifested through the artist's work, gradually began to be rejected.³ Thus, it became increasingly difficult to distinguish the line between art and kitsch: objects became industrialized, worn out, banalised and without any originality. As soon as pleasure was achieved, the object would lose its purpose due to its lack of value and identity, it would become worthless. For such a culture, it did not matter whether the Rembrandt painting on the wall was a copy or an original, what mattered was that it served its function. Art from then on became relative, "in the eye of the beholder", and no longer found its footing in virtue, but only in the farce of originality, entering the death and oblivion of its own identity. Therefore, culture began to strive for the missing purity provided by the idea of absolute music, where the composition had its own identity, a virtue, to which purpose and value did not need to be given because it was already contained in itself.⁴

Artists began to rebel against kitsch and false, uneducated culture, where more and more works were created within the framework of functional art, according to pleasure and desire.⁵ This led to the development of new musical and aesthetic directions, built on pentatonic and symmetrical scales, extended harmony, tone painting, etc.⁶ But from that initial idea, composers began to seek purity and independence through their originality, which led to what the fight was originally against: the absence of standards and the renunciation of identity for the sake of rebellion, thus creating a constant rebellion against what is already rebellious. The biggest disadvantage of this is that no new idea can be fully "digested" or made conscious because there is nothing by which it would be clear that it is new. What was originally conceived as shocking or disgusting, becomes predictable and boring through repetition and thus loses its significance.

The development of art music throughout the 20th century was marked by a gradual decadence of values, making it increasingly impossible to create a *Gesamtmusikwerk*, a piece of music that includes all musical components, where the value of the composition is found in the work itself.

By rejecting tonality, composers began to use four remaining possibilities (and their interpretations) that have no hierarchical tonal value: the first is that the tones become equal to each other, as is the case in the dodecaphonic system; the second is for each tone to become independent, without relation to any other tone in the composition, like the idea of punctualism; the third possibility is that the tonal value becomes random, like the idea of aleatorics, and the fourth and last possibility is to reject the very concept of tone, like the composition 4:33 by John Cage. The greatest flaw of such musical directions is that their entire idea is based on the rejection of hierarchical value, and not on its expansion, as is the case with the music of

² MEYER (1984), 23 – 24.

³ GRAHAM (1997), 5.

⁴ DAHLHAUS (1989, 1991), 3.

⁵ DICK (1997), 6.

⁶ ROLLIN (1997), 24

Beethoven or Wagner. Such music becomes deprived of its own function to the extent that it is deprived of its structure, and it is absurd to listen to it by itself, without a given external function - such as its combination with a film scene, or its shaping into descriptive, program music. As with everything else, the less visible the form and structure, the less visible the purpose.

In Germany during the 1920s, the National Socialist Party under the leadership of Adolf Hitler began to accuse such artists and composers of atonal music of committing culturicide and destroying the millennial values that had built the West, especially singling out Jews, since they were the majority composers of atonal and avant-garde music. In order to promote avant-garde music, Nazi Germany accused them of culturicide, declaring their music degenerative, distorted - "Entartete musik".⁷ After the war, an artistic revolt against classical values began because they were promoted by Nazism. One of the most dominant influences of the period was the so-called Darmstadt School, a group of composers after World War II who shaped the aesthetics of music as we know it, beginning their work through the cultural denazification of Germany.⁸ However, this project has been going on for 80 years and is being tried to be applied to the entire Western world, as if they were all part of the Third Reich.

Friedrich Nietzsche would predict this situation, saying that the West had experienced its Apollonian peak, its apotheosis - like the Roman Empire - and after that peak, the spirit would eventually die out, like an aging champion, to be replaced and overcome by the Dionysian spirit, a return to the potential, the decadence of the society from which it all began, awaiting a new spirit from which Apollonian maturity could grow again.⁹

Therefore, many would say that the arrival of atonal music was inevitable, hinted at since the Baroque era and the very beginnings of tonality, where equalizing the relationship between intervals made it possible to play all tonalities on one polyphonic instrument¹⁰. Because of that, supporters of atonal and avant-garde music believe that, if the equalization of intervals led to the liberation of the possibilities of tonality, so too will the equalization of the values of the same intervals free up new musical possibilities, gradually beginning the liberation of music from other systems of formation.

From this, art has become crippled because it no longer represents the logos but rather proclaims itself as the logos, exclaiming: I am who I am! The West has taken the very shadow for its spirit, and no one dares to say this lest they be called a supporter of Nazism, as if the Nazis had written out Western values. The loss of identity leads to the rejection of tonality and every other system of formation in music and art - the fundamental values and symbols by which civilization was guided. Such an approach does not lead to the development of culture, but to its deliberate destruction, in which anything that even remotely resembles identity is torn away.

Avant-garde and postmodernist music is limited because it does not have its own identity, which is why it can only represent an anti-heroic character, which depicts the disintegration of one's identity. Thus, no hero or person of a healthy, strong spirit can identify his life and work with such music, because it is anti-heroic (this does not apply to the creation of music, which is heroic in itself). Since such music is deprived of its own function, this means that its spirit, i.e. identity, is non-existent, thereby proving that such music is guided by a shadow, not a spirit. A shadow, which does not have its own matter, always depends on someone else's body, structure - so avant-garde music depends on a given external function, since it cannot stand alone, it does not have its own identity. We come to the end of music, its death, because if there is no invisible, there is no visible presentation of the invisible.¹¹

Most music theorists will describe this criticism as another shallow attempt at cultural regression and preventing the development of music, declaring that tonality, along with the very concept of consonance and dissonance, is just a cultural invention like any other, an outdated system that needed to be outgrown and replaced. Paul Hindemith will say about the concept of

⁷ SAMAMA (2004), 13.

⁸ IDDON (2013), 13-14.

⁹ NIETZSCHE (1872, 2008), 9.

¹⁰ WERCKMEISTER (1707, 2018), 34.

¹¹ NANCY (1996), 93.

consonance and dissonance: "The two concepts have never been completely explained, and for a thousand years the definitions have varied".¹² However, it should be emphasized that I am not writing here about cultural adaptations of consonance and dissonance, but about them as an inseparable part of the collective spirit, defined by Carl Gustav Jung,¹³ as well as the laws of acoustics.¹⁴ Thus, their existence cannot be disputed, as well as the existence of tonality, the result of the unification of all previous musical systems into a single, coherent system.

Every flaw of postmodernist and avant-garde music is, on the one hand, also its advantage, something that can make it sincere, but often pathetic in relation to other musical styles and forms. From a psychoanalytic perspective, tonality in music correlates with the concept of identity, and atonality with the concept of shadow. According to Nietzsche and Jung, confronting and integrating with one's own shadow is necessary for a person to be able to free and realize identity, to become part of one's own whole. The relationship between atonality and tonality should be approached in the same way, by enabling their potential cooperation, but also by objectively giving space for the creation of other styles.

¹² HINDEMITH (1942, 1945), 85.

¹³ JUNG (1954, 1980), 20.

¹⁴ PIERCE (1989), 3-4, 65.

2 Contratonality and multitonality – a skipped stage of the development of music

Was atonality really an inevitable part of music? What if the West managed to perfect only the Ionian-Aeolian system, the fundamental, but not the only possible system of tonality? The development of music could have been built upon by discovering other subordinate harmonic systems and their rules within tonality, and not just by rejecting and abandoning the entire concept of tonality as such.¹⁵ Indications of the emergence of tonality as we know it begin in the late Middle Ages (through the discipline of the quadrivium), where the union of geometry and music led to the discovery of the musical heptagram, built from the progression of the circle of fifths.¹⁶

Mesopotamia, Tablet CBS 1766, 1st millennium BC.¹⁷ The discovered tablet shows for the first time in the history of music that we know of a musical heptagram, the earliest evidence of the use of the heptatonic system in music.

The first heptatonic systems emerged from the musical heptagram, so it is logical to conclude that it influenced the formation of the tonal system as we know it. There is no direct evidence for its existence in the Middle Ages, but the entire concept of musical education at the time suggests that it did. The heptagram, as it was built according to the circle of fifths, also points to a new system of harmony that was to follow: thus, coordinate harmony, or *tonalité ancienne* (one that does not have a purposeful development in its movement, whose movement arises only from the relationship of neighboring chords) would gradually be replaced in the late Renaissance by subordinate, hierarchical harmony, the one we know today.¹⁸

¹⁵ DAHLHAUS (1990), 141-142.

¹⁶ WELLS (2019), 1.

¹⁷ FRIBERG (2011), 129.

¹⁸ DAHLHAUS (1990), 12.

A harmonic heptagram, formed from a movement of fifths within the diatonic scale (IV-VII-III-VI-II-V-I). This heptagram emerged from an analysis of Bach's pieces (such as Fugue in G minor, BWV 578), with placing the progression of movement of fifths in a circle, a symbol of perfection.

Just as tonality developed from the musical heptagram, so another tonal system, unprecedented in the history of music, could develop and take shape, with functions, i.e. values diametrically opposed to tonality as we know it – contratonality. The form of contratonality was indirectly initiated through the acoustic scale (from the diatonic system of Béla Bartók), made of opposite tetrachords in relation to the major scale: C-D-E-F# - G-A-Bb-C.¹⁹

The acoustic scale can be used as a substitute for dissonant functions of tonality, such as the dominant, whose function and reason for existence could not be properly understood only from the perspective of the tonal system. In the tonal system, the function of the tonic is tonal, consonant, and the dominant (which is not necessarily only on the 5th degree) is contratonal, dissonant, thus creating a perfect relationship of consonance and dissonance, tonality and contratonality. The existence of contratonality opens the question of the existence of multitonality, a term that refers to the potential existence of multiple tonal systems from the musical heptagram.

¹⁹ LENDVAI (1971, 1979), 67.

Tonality as we know it, i.e the concept of major and minor, derives from 2 modes – Ionic and Aeolian. Each mode also derives from two other modes: for example, the major scale, i.e. the Ionic mode, derives from the lower tetrachord of the Mixolydian and the upper tetrachord of the Lydian modes. The arrangement of these modes in the tonality forms the main harmonic degrees of the tonality (I – IV – V). In the same way, the minor scale arises, which in classical harmony comes in 3 forms, to compensate for the discarded Locrian mode (as shown).

The characteristic dissonances of classical harmony are indirectly the results of the contratonal system. For example, if the concept of contratinality is used on the 5th degree of the major or minor scale, it will result in a dominant seventh chord, a secondary dominant of the second degree, an augmented seventh chord, and a diminished chord. The contratonal system itself arises from the chromatic change of the most dissonant interval of the major scale – the tritone, built on the 4th and 7th degrees of the diatonic scale.

The proposed system cannot be built on the minor (Aeolian mode) because the Aeolian mode in the heptagram is built from the tetrachords of the Dorian and Phrygian modes. This is important because the Dorian and Phrygian modes, along with the Ionian, are the only three modes built from identical tetrachords. Thus, the construction of counter-tonality is possible only through these 3 modes. If the counter-tonal system is built on the remaining 2 modes mentioned, like the Phrygian mode, the scale of the melodic minor is obtained (E-F#-G-A - B-C#-D#-E), the expected complement to the discontinuity of the Locrian mode in the heptagram. If the contratinality is to be built on the Dorian mode, the scale of D-E-F#-G - A-Bb-C-D is obtained, therefore a variant of counter-tonality with its identical tones. Also visible again is the characteristic change of tritones on the tones F and B. I leave the harmonic possibilities of the presented forms open for future study and completion.

The contratonal system completes the theory of classical harmony, opens up the possibility of new tonal systems and enhances the new compositional technique, calling for the renewal of the Western spirit.

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Kontratonalitet i multitonaitet kao nova rješenja krize tonaliteta u umjetničkoj glazbi

Članak se temelji na dva dijela. Prvi dio bavi se tematikom duboke krize tonaliteta u suvremenoj umjetničkoj glazbi, koja je prvenstveno oblikovana i utjecana kroz kulturološke i političke borbe kraja 19. i 20. stoljeća. Od tada do danas prevladava stav da su sve mogućnosti tonaliteta iscrpljene, stoga njegovo korištenje može voditi samo u banalnost i cliché. Drugi dio članka bavi se neistraženim dijelovima tonaliteta i po prvi puta će predložiti direktnu definiciju podrijetla tonaliteta. Novi sustav disonance koji je predstavljen je nazvan kontratonalitet, kao suprotnost tonalitetu, sustavu konsonance, a samo njegovo postojanje predlaže postojanje više tonalnih sustava, što dovodi do teorije multitonaiteta.